

TDiFf Bug List

DataFrame Category	Polars	PySpark	Pandas-compatible	Total
Bug Count	19	8	15	42

* The Issue URL contains a detailed bug report.

Polars:

No	DataFrame Category	DataFrame System	Bug Category	Trigger Pattern	Issue URL*	Status
1	Polars	Polars	Crash	Native vs. Memory Optimization	Polars #25544	Fixed
2	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. Memory Optimization	Polars #25072	Fixed
3	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. Memory Optimization	Polars #25592	Fixed
4	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #25160	Fixed
5	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #25182	Fixed
6	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #25210	Fixed
7	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #25211	Fixed
8	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #25604	Fixed

No	DataFrame Category	DataFrame System	Bug Category	Trigger Pattern	Issue URL*	Status
9	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #25575	Fixed
10	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #26163	Fixed
11	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #26248	Fixed
12	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #26187	Fixed
13	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #26186	Confirmed
14	Polars	Polars	Logical	Native vs. Lazy Execution	Polars #26150	Fixed
15	Polars	Polars	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #25549	Fixed
16	Polars	Polars	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #25564	Fixed
17	Polars	Polars	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #25616	Fixed
18	Polars	Polars	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	Polars #26188	Confirmed
19	Polars	Polars	Error	Native vs. Memory Optimization	Polars #25098	Not a Bug

PySpark:

No	DataFrame Category	DataFrame System	Bug Category	Trigger Pattern	Issue URL*	Status
1	PySpark	PySpark	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	PySpark #13907	Fixed
2	PySpark	PySpark	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	PySpark #13914	Fixed
3	PySpark	PySpark	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	PySpark #13731	Fixed
4	PySpark	PySpark	Error	Native vs. GPU Execution	PySpark #13925	Confirmed
5	PySpark	PySpark	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	PySpark #13704	Confirmed
6	PySpark	PySpark	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	PySpark #13728	Confirmed
7	PySpark	PySpark	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	PySpark #14169	Confirmed
8	PySpark	PySpark	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	PySpark #14168	Confirmed

Pandas-compatible:

No	DataFrame Category	DataFrame System	Bug Category	Trigger Pattern	Issue URL*	Status
1	Pandas-compatible	Pandas	Crash	Native vs. Distributed Execution	Pandas #63630	Confirmed
2	Pandas-compatible	Dask	Logical	Native vs. Distributed Execution	Dask #12237	Fixed
3	Pandas-compatible	Dask	Logical	Native vs. Distributed Execution	Dask #12172	Confirmed
4	Pandas-compatible	Dask	Logical	Native vs. Distributed Execution	Dask #12176	Confirmed
5	Pandas-compatible	Dask	Error	Native vs. Distributed Execution	Dask #12251	Waiting
6	Pandas-compatible	CuDF	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	CuDF #20746	Fixed
7	Pandas-compatible	CuDF	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	CuDF #20728	Confirmed
8	Pandas-compatible	CuDF	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	CuDF #21082	Confirmed
9	Pandas-compatible	CuDF	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	CuDF #21136	Confirmed
10	Pandas-compatible	CuDF	Logical	Native vs. GPU	CuDF #20761	Waiting

No	DataFrame Category	DataFrame System	Bug Category	Trigger Pattern	Issue URL*	Status
				Execution		
11	Pandas-compatible	CuDF	Logical	Native vs. GPU Execution	CuDF #21137	Not a Bug
12	Pandas-compatible	Modin	Logical	Native vs. Parallel Execution	Modin #7692	Waiting
13	Pandas-compatible	Modin	Logical	Native vs. Parallel Execution	Modin #7693	Waiting
14	Pandas-compatible	Modin	Logical	Native vs. Parallel Execution	Modin #7694	Waiting
15	Pandas-compatible	Pandas on PySpark	Logical	Native vs. Distributed Execution	PySpark #54666	Fixed